

From induction to emergence from anesthesia: slow waves and infraslow rhythmic microarousal-like events

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Background. Spontaneous brain states, characterized by distinct spatiotemporal activity patterns, play a fundamental role in information processing, cognitive flexibility, and behavior, and serve as reliable biomarkers of consciousness levels, sleep stages, and cortical pathology. Anesthesia levels offer a highly controlled experimental condition to precisely monitor these brain states and investigate the temporal dynamics underlying transitions between unconsciousness and wakefulness.

Methods. We investigated brain activity in 11 chronically implanted rats across a total of 24 ketamine-medetomidine anesthesia sessions (5–6 hours each), with several animals undergoing multiple sessions. Local field potentials and multiunit activity were recorded from multiple cortical regions, along with electromyography and video recordings, we outlined a sequential progression of neural dynamics from anesthesia induction through recovery, quantifying oscillatory patterns, firing rates, and temporal structure.

Results. Induction rapidly shifted cortical dynamics from irregular, asynchronous awake activity to rhythmic slow oscillations (~1.58 Hz; 95% CI: 1.43–1.72 Hz). During emergence, as anesthesia lightened, cortical activity alternated between theta-dominant episodes (~5.64 Hz; 95% CI: 5.36–5.91 Hz) and microarousal-like events, transient desynchronized periods with elevated firing rates. This alternation was initially organized by an infraslow rhythm (~0.1 Hz) that progressively slowed as microarousal-like events lengthened, accompanied by rising muscle tone and spontaneous movements. Late microarousal-like events showed increasing high-frequency power, gradually approaching awake-like spectral profiles. Microarousal-like event durations exhibited heavy-tailed distributions compatible with a power-law over an intermediate range (population $\alpha = 2.69$; 95% CI: 2.43–2.94), observed consistently across subjects and sessions.

Conclusions. These findings characterize a reproducible sequence of cortical states and transitions during induction and prolonged emergence from ketamine/medetomidine anesthesia in rats. The structured progression of microarousal-like events, with infraslow rhythmic organization early in Emergence, heavy-tailed duration distributions, and gradual spectral/behavioral evolution toward wakefulness, describes a gradual, multi-timescale trajectory toward wakefulness, providing new clues about the cortical dynamics driving recovery of consciousness under this anesthetic regimen while establishing microarousal-like events as dependable indicators of the return to wakefulness.

